

Review

Peter Croton, *A Method for the Baroque Lute based on Historical Sources* (Le Luth Doré, Paris, 2022.). xiii + 337pp. ISMN: 377-0-0017-8840-1.

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Instruction books for modern musical instruments often reflect the views of the author's teacher as well as their own experiences of playing in modern orchestras/ensembles. Since these instruments are, by definition, still in present day use there is general consensus (or near) on the appropriate playing techniques and such a personal approach is therefore usually acceptable. Perhaps not so understandable is for authors of modern tutors for early (period) instruments to adopt a similar approach based on their own experiences and those of their teacher with relatively little reference to historical evidence. This is especially a concern for those instruments which do not have an unbroken playing tradition down to modern times – such as the lute. And, indeed, some modern lute methods can merely present the personal views of an individual player also regurgitating other modern players' questionable practices, rather than historical evidence. It is partly this lacuna which Peter Croton aims to address in this new lute tutor specifically for the later baroque period instrument and the attempt is to be much applauded. It offers a practical (if rather wordy) guide on holding, fingering and plucking the instrument with appropriate musical examples from early sources. But also, and this is where his tutor is different to most others, a long discursion on background matters (including rhetoric, musical style, anatomy) and the presentation of certain historical evidence. Indeed, Croton says he finds such general background material 'useful for understanding rhetorically-expressive playing and healthy, balanced body use'. But, recognising that this may not suit all students, he goes on to say that 'knowledgeable or impatient readers may, however, wish to skip to Part IV, the actual baroque lute method.....'.

This new publication by the specialist French publishing house, Le Luth Doré, is presented in a music page size (9x12in/230 x 310mm) suitable for most stands and has a very substantial 337 pages. At €108 (about £90) the price is pretty steep although, perhaps, not too high in view of the size of the tome and the insights into some historical aspects of playing this type of lute. The space devoted to general background matters and to some selected historical evidence fills almost the entire first half of the book before the first piece of musical (tablature) notation appears in Chapter 4. Croton is rightly uneasy at calling the instrument a 'baroque lute', since this is a modern term, but chooses to employ it for convenience rather than a descriptor such as '11+ course lute'. As an aside, and not mentioned by Croton, is that the term 'baroque lute' could also equally as well refer to the theorboed lute (*liuto attiorbato*) used in Italy through the 17th into the late 18th century and to the six/seven course *mandora/gallichon* mostly found in German speaking lands throughout the same period).

The work is divided into 7 chapters ('Parts') prefaced by acknowledgements and detailed contents, followed by an extensive (10 sides) bibliography of primary and secondary sources.

The first chapters cover:

- *Tools of rhetorical expression* (historically inspired, rhetorical performance, consonance /dissonance, phrasing/articulation, dynamics, movement, ornamentation etc);
- *Introduction to relevant anatomy & biomechanics* (movements of the body, arm and fingers as they relate to lute playing);
- *Preparing to play* (mental/psychological and physical preparation for playing);

These are followed by chapters on the actual technique of how to play the instrument:

- *Stage 1* preparatory exercises and suggestions for fingering and expression (tuning, stringing and fretting; tablature; holding the lute; right hand position and use of fingers; left hand; ornamentation; various progressive technical exercises, practising);
- *Stage 2* (body movement; more complex pieces and chords; raking/brushing play);
- *Stage 3* (even more advanced works);
- *Introduction to basso continuo* (style; voice leading; realisation of figured bass, rule of the octave; specimen realisations).

Despite detailed descriptions of many aspects of lute playing, some crucial areas of technique are not comprehensively explored. For example: the important instructions for the new (from the late 16th century) right hand technique could have benefited from a fuller and separate dedicated section rather than being spread over various dispersed and loosely connected paragraphs. It would have also been helpful to include original period illustrations showing lute players' hand posture in this period. Nevertheless, Croton is to be applauded by being one of few to also describe and advocate the clearly documented plucking hand positioned close to or even on the bridge. This produces a brilliant and articulate sound, as then preferred by lutenists in the baroque period, rather than the earlier close to the rose position adopted by many modern players for the entire lute repertoire and which gives a soft, mellow homogeneous tone.

Croton also points out that the new 'thumb-out' plucking manner became increasingly employed from the later 16th century and that by the 1620s it was the default plucking technique. Sadly, the anachronistic employment of the earlier 'thumb-under' technique for the later lute repertoire is nowadays growing in popularity and even becoming the fashionable choice (perhaps to further distinguish for audiences the noble lute from its abhorred relative - the modern classical guitar - which was, ironically, the first instrument of many modern lutenists). In fact, 'thumb-out' plucking remained the general technique for the rest of the historical lute's existence. However, it is precisely this clearly documented and historically preferred playing style which is nowadays frequently denied by many lutenists performing works from the early baroque period onwards. Indeed, despite published papers pointing out the 'fakery' of the 'thumb-under' technique for much of the lute repertoire, its use persists and even grows.¹

Regarding holding the lute, the tutor recommends using a strap around the shoulders but early depictions often do not show such a support. Moreover, many extant lutes have two buttons on the back of the instrument - one by the neck joint and one at the base - and an early practice was to tie a cord between the two which is hooked around a button on the player's coat.

¹Jeremy Montagu and Martyn Hodgson, 'More on Fakery in Period Performance', *Early Music Performer* 51 (2022).

In fact, such cord loops have even survived on some extant instruments (eg Stautinger 1773, Castle Museum, York): this historical method of supporting the instrument is not mentioned in the tutor. Unusually the book also advocates playing the later (11+ course) lute standing up, but there is very little early evidence to support this position. In fact most depictions show the 17th/18th century instrument being played seated with the instrument resting on the right thigh (and not down in the lap as Croton demonstrates). It would have been helpful to have good reproductions of early illustrations (paintings/engravings) showing the lute being played during this period (such as the informative 1690 depiction of Charles Mouton).

Whilst a few modern lutenists make use of 'raking and brushing' play (*tirer et rebattre*), which was *de rigueur* in the earlier/mid 17th century especially for the French repertoire, the tutor only briefly mentions the technique linked to chord arpeggiation, but without describing the light down and up strumming refined style of play required. The graded examples and pieces selected from a wide repertoire are good for learners and I especially welcome the use of fret symbols placed on the tablature line (the general historical manner and easiest to read) rather than between the lines as found in some modern editions of lute music. However, despite covering a much wider range of topics than do most modern lute tutors, the book overlooks some other important areas, including: different sizes of 'baroque' lutes and increasing string length into the eighteenth century; early pitches; types of strings employed on lutes of the period; string tension based on historical evidence; 'sharp' tunings (ie not just the Dm tuning) even in this later period; development of the 12 and 13 course lute and the later German 'theorboed' version.

The author's approach is laudable in many ways, not the least by making modern lute players aware of some historical evidence, but it is rather wordy and much of the rambling text could have done with the attentions of a good editor. Nevertheless, the work goes towards filling various gaps in lute instruction books currently available and Croton is to be thanked for this. His books for the earlier ('renaissance') lute, guitar and theorbo have also been published and the first 'background' chapters of this latest work repeats much of what has already appeared in these.